

ELEMNETY KINOPOETYKI W NIEFIKCYJNYM ROMANSIE TRUMANA CAPOTE «IN COLD BLOOD»

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Adnotacja. W artykule przeanalizowano szczególną stylową paletę romansu T. Capote «In Cold Blood» zbudowanego na faktach życia realnego, teksty którego są prezentowane czytelnikowi jako ekspresywne, wyodrębnione barwne kadry-fragmenty, powołane w celu przedstawienia nowej różnorodności gatunkowej - romansu niefikcyjnego. Zbadano wykorzystanie przedsięwzięć kinematograficznych.

Ponieważ główną zasadą stworzenia obrazu kinowego jest zasada montażu, to właśnie z jego pomocą pisarz łączy kadry, czyli fragmenty rzeczywistości, ustawia w odpowiedniej kolejności plany obrazu, "robi "dystylację" znaczących detali, ujęcia przestrzenne itd. Połączenie fragmentów stanowi poligraficzną strukturę książki, która jest uzupełniona opowieściami o bohaterach, czyli są oni charakteryzowani z różnych pozycji, m. in. dzięki zabiegom kinematograficznym. Narracja romansu w całości odpowiada zadaniom i charakterystyce powieści klasycznej: przedstawia bohaterów obiektywnie - w działaniu, wydarzeniach, relacjach z innymi bohaterami i jednocześnie daje możliwość czytelnikowi zajrzeć do ich świata wewnętrznego.

Słowa kluczowe: reportaż, nonfiction, zabieg kinematograficzny, montaż, kompozycja, fabuła, zbliżenie, kadr.

THE ELEMENTS OF FILM POETICS IN THE NONFICTION NOVEL «IN COLD BLOOD» BY TRUMAN CAPOTE

Abstract. The especial style palette of the novel «In Cold Blood» by Truman Capote was analyzed in the article. The novel is based on the facts of real life. The novel is presented to the reader as expressive vivid shots which are used to show a new art form – nonfiction novel. The use of the cinematic techniques was studied.

The main principle of film image is the principle of cutting. The writer combines different shots, shifts them, zooms and cuts to highlight certain details. The combination of different plots makes up a polyphonic structure of the book. The narration fits in the tasks and characteristics of the classical storytelling: it presents the characters objectively and at the same time it lets the reader look into their inner world.

Keywords: reportage, nonfiction, cinematic technique, cutting, composition, plot, close-up, shot.

ЕЛЕМЕНТИ КІНОПОЕТИКИ В НЕФІКЦІЙНОМУ РОМАНІ ТРУМЕНА КАПОТЕ «IN COLD BLOOD»

Анотація. В статті проаналізовано особливу стильову палітру роману Т. Капоте «In Cold Blood», побудованого на фактах реального життя, текст якого представлено читачеві як експресивні, виокремлені яскраві кадри-фрагменти, покликані унаочнити нову жанрову різновидність – нефікційний роман. Досліджено використання кінематографічних прийомів.

Оскільки основним принципом створення кінообразу є принцип монтажу, саме за його допомогою письменник поєднує кадри, тобто фрагменти дійсності, чергує плани

зображуваного, «дистильоване» значимі деталі, просторові ракурси тощо. Поєднання сюжетних ліній складає поліфонічну структуру книги, яка доповнюється оповідями про героїв, тобто вони характеризуються з різних позицій, у тому числі завдяки кінематографічним прийомам, Нарація роману цілком відповідає завданням і характеристикам класичної розповіді: вона представляє персонажів об'єктивно – у вчинках, подіях, стосунках з іншими героями – і водночас дає змогу читачеві зазирнути в їхній внутрішній світ.

Ключові слова: репортаж, нонфікшн, кінематографічний прийом, монтаж, композиція, сюжет, крупний план, кадр.

Stating the scientific problem and its meaning. The works of Truman Streckfus Capote (1924 – 1984), a cult American writer and screenwriter, belong to the vivid phenomena of the American literary process of the XXth century. The peculiarity of the writer's works is his studying the world using his spiritual experience and his original understanding of reality. The writer was unique due to his ability not only to choose the themes but to find specific methods and techniques to interpret them. The world sensation was the publication of the nonfiction novel «In Cold Blood. A True Account Of Multiple Murder And Its Consequences» (1965). The writer made an original genre experiment – he created a nonfiction novel (as he labeled it), initially it was a magazine edition and then a literary work. The novel initiated a new trend, New Journalism, in the American literature in the 1960 – 1970s. The unusual and complex literary organization of the novel «In Cold Blood» by Truman Capote attracted the attention of the literary scholars and critics. Blurring genre bounds and even unusual risky combination of the techniques of fiction and documents, including the elements of film elements are the distinctive characteristics of Capote's narrative.

Nowadays as before the readers, scholars and cultural workers are interested in the novel «In Cold Blood» by Truman Capote. The research made by William L. Nance («The Worlds of Truman Capote», 1970) and Kenneth T. Reed («Truman Capote», 1981) are still fundamental works for studying Capote's works especially the novel «In Cold Blood». J. De Bellis, G. Clarke, J. Hollowell, G. Garrett, D. Galloway, M. Zavazadeh, S. Kauffmann, H. Kramer, D. McDonald, J. Knowles, D. Pizer, G. Steiner, S. Yurick, W. Phillips and others studied the problems of genre uniqueness of the work, the use of techniques and methods of movie, facts, journalism in the novel.

The works of the Ukrainian and Russian scientists are devoted to the problem of nonfiction in the American literature of the second half of the XXth century. We should mention the famous works by Zh. Konovalova, O. Taranenko, M. Turovska, K. Stetsenko. Unfortunately, the novel «In Cold Blood» is almost unfamiliar to the Ukrainian readers. During the times of the Soviet Union one couldn't interpret this novel unprejudiced and critically. In the research of the famous Ukrainian and Russian scientists T. Denysova («Contemporary American Novel», 1976, «The History Of The American Literature Of The XXth Century», 2010) and O. Zverev («The Lonely Dreamers of Truman Capote», 1974, «Spiral Turns», 2001) the attention is concentrated on some social problems rather than on the complex analysis of the novel. O. Zverev defines the main plots, analyzes the characters, the reasons of their actions in his articles. T. Denysova concentrates on the genre of the work. Moreover, the literary study of the nonfiction novel “In Cold Blood” is far from completion. Despite the high professionalism of the stated works, the principles of movie as an important peculiarity of the style of the nonfiction novel were not studied. The actuality of the problems of

the research is defined by the necessity of literary understanding of the interactivity of literature and cinema, especially at the level of descriptive systems. At present stage the analysis becomes complicated because of the absence of the full translation of the work into Ukrainian.

The aim of the article is to analyze the elements of film techniques as a peculiar characteristic of the style of the nonfiction novel «In Cold Blood» by Truman Capote.

Statement of the materials and explanation of the received results of the research. In September 1965 the nonfiction novel «In Cold Blood» by Truman Capote was serialized in *The New Yorker* (25.09; 02.10; 09.10; 16.10; Capote worked as a reporter in *The New Yorker*). Ten weeks later in December 1966 it was published in book form by Random House. The book was copyrighted a month later. The title was translated as «The Ordinary Murder» in many countries of the world. The book was a result of six-year-old research based on the interviews with criminals and witnesses, official records, correspondence, court records, extended interviews, newspaper / magazine accounts, diary entries and reports on this event. The phenomenon of the «youth riot» and its consequences was called a contemporary «American tragedy» by the critics. The novel «In Cold Blood» is unusual due to Capote's striving for depicting not only the accuracy of the facts, documents, relationships of cause and effect of the depicted events, but create a new art form.

The novel «In Cold Blood» wasn't the writer's first attempt in nonfiction. Before that he had written four nonfiction works, or travel sketches: «Local Colour» (1950), «The Muses Are Heard» (1956), «The Duke In His Domain» (1957) and «Portraits and Observations» published after his death (2001). J. Hollowell pointed out «The Muses Are Heard» and «The Duke In His Domain», biographical sketches about Marlon Brando, became important periods in the professional life of the author (*see Hollowell, 1977, p. 65*). Capote in his interview to Plimpton stated that he hadn't tried ambitious reportages by 1956 when he wrote a sketch – «The Muses Are Heard», an account of the first theatrical cultural exchange of the USA and the USSR – «Porgy & Bess» about a tour in Russia. «The Muses Are Heard» was published in *The New Yorker*, the only magazine encouraging serious writers of this art form. Then Capote felt he could create a full-footed narrative in other words a nonfiction novel, he harbored this decision over twenty years ago (*see Plimpton, 1968, p. 25*). Many years later Capote said: «I wanted a narrative form that employed all the techniques of fictional art but was nevertheless immaculately factual» (*Plimpton, 1968, p. 26*). «I wanted to write what I called a nonfiction novel – a book that would be read exactly like a novel except that every word of it would be absolutely true» (*Grobel, 1985, p. 112*). The author recollected that in «The Muses Are Heard» he employed cutting, retrospective and kept to the fiction style (*see Hollowell, 1977, p. 66*). The writer used other plots to create a nonfiction novel but they had failed before the case of the Cutters had happened. Even this choice depended upon the emergence of Perry. The author wrote the book due to Smith. In conclusion, the meeting of the prototypes and their characters was one of the premises to write a nonfiction novel, another reason was to invent a new art form. Due to Dick's photographic memory the author managed to portray the behavior of the murderers after the crime and before their arrest in details. The author's feelings portray a deep conflict between human pain and art necessity.

The history of the most important book is well-known. Capote told it a lot of times. On Monday, November 16, 1959 he picked up a copy of the *New York Times*

and noticed on an inside page a 300-word article about a strange cruel murder of a farmer, his wife and their two children in their provincial town: «Holcomb, Kan., Nov. 15 (UPI) – A wealthy wheat farmer, his wife and their two young children were found shot to death today in their home. They had been killed by shotgun blasts at close range after being bound and gagged. The father, 48-year-old Herbert W. Clutter, was found in the basement with his son, Kenyon, 15. His wife Bonnie, 45, and a daughter, Nancy, 16, were in their beds. There were no signs of a struggle, and nothing had been stolen. The telephone lines had been cut. “This is apparently the case of a psychopathic killer,” Sheriff Earl Robinson said. Mr. Clutter was founder of the Kansas Wheat Growers Association. In 1954, President Eisenhower appointed him to the Federal Farm Credit Board, but he never lived in Washington. The board represents the twelve farm credit districts in the country. Mr. Clutter served from December, 1953, until April, 1957. He declined a reappointment. He was also a local member of the Agriculture Department's Price Stabilization Board and was active with the Great Plains Wheat Growers Association. The Clutter farm and ranch cover almost 1,000 acres in one of the richest wheat areas. Mr. Clutter, his wife and daughter were clad in pajamas. The boy was wearing blue jeans and a T-shirt. The bodies were discovered by two of Nancy's classmates, Susan Kidwell and Nancy Ewalt» (*Malin, 1968, p.7*).

There was nothing sensational in this report. It was an ordinary report of the ordinary murder. Capote stated the reason of his interest in this murder was his wish to make an experiment in journalism and that's why he was looking for a definite theme: «... would be the ideal subject matter for the massive job of reportage I wanted to do» (*Reed, 1981, p. 102*). «What I think is that reporting can be made as interesting as fiction, and done as artistically» (*Plimpton, 1966, p. 27*). He managed to invent a new art novel form, demonstrate a new style of writing combining various perspectives, points of view, factual documentary materials and their literary journalistic and psychological interpretation, including the elements of other forms of art, first of all, cinema.

We can see the peculiarity of the writer's art thinking in the images he created according to the rules of painting. This explains the presence of expressive coded visual scenes-«shots» in the text. They are edited from different scenes of various shots skillfully – from long shots to middle and close-ups according to the principles of film editing. The principle of composition of the author seems to be simple – portraying life, crime and death, but different events, detailed account of all the circumstances and collisions, a number of characters, psychological justification of their behavior, the objective position of the narrator made it difficult to choose and orchestrate the plot of the novel. So, there is no plot as we understand it in the novel. The novel can be studied as a film script of a director with the plot realized through detailed mise-en-scenes. The reader has to construct the chronological sequence of the events by himself. The composition harmony is due to the principles of cutting. This approach was worked out by the practice of film art and it means the selection of the best episodes to create an entire film or story combining them. Capote used a cutting method selecting real events, editing the best episodes and combining different sections of the text. Moreover, Capote's storytelling is aimed at reasonability perfectly. The titles of four parts have a prognostic function: Part 1 – The Last To See Them Alive; Part 2 – Persons Unknown; Part 3 – Answer; Part 4 – The Corner. Every part consists of a definite number of sections resembling the shots of the film. The real content of the novel «In Cold Blood»

is in the form of changing cut shots. The use of different types of film cutting – parallel cutting, contrast editing – causes the best efficiency of narrative discourse.

The author employs the method by contradiction in the novel which is the characteristic of cutting the composition. The narration doesn't start with the sensational information about the murder but with the panorama of the crime scene. The usual nature and ordinary farmer's life are described skillfully. «The village of Holcomb stands on the high wheat plains of western Kansas, a lonesome area that other Kansans call 'out there.' Some seventy miles east of the Colorado border, the countryside, with its hard blue skies and desert-clear air, has an atmosphere that is rather more Far West than Middle West. <...> Holcomb, too, can be seen from great distances. Not that there's much to see – simply an aimless congregation of buildings divided in the center by the main-line tracks of the Santa Fe Rail-road, a haphazard hamlet bounded on the south by a brown stretch of the Arkansas (pronounced 'Ar-kan-sas) River, on the north by a highway, Route 50, and on the east and west by prairie lands and wheat fields» (*Capote, 1994, p. 3*).

Initially an exciting plot isn't expected in eventless Holcomb. Time seems to stop here, space seems to be restricted, a circle of interests seems to narrow and all the random events seem to disappear. The writer showed amazing skills to describe it vividly. Due to his descriptions the reader becomes a viewer, onlooker of the described landscape (mime). That's why J. Hollowell calls the beginning of the novel «In Cold Blood» «you-are-there effect» (*Hollowell, 1977, p. 69-70*).

Then the author shifts the shot shifting the story to the farm River Valley. In close shot we can see The Clutters and criminals, short shots of Kansas life and psychological close-ups of the murderers.

After introducing the owner of the farm River Valley Herbert Clutter (eating apples and drinking a glass of milk) in the first narrative episode the author starts introducing his murderer by an intriguing phrase: «Like Mr. Clutter, the young man breakfasting in a cafe called the Little Jewel never drank coffee» (*Capote, 1994, p. 14*). The author employs the sounds – car horn – to shift the scene from the murderers to the Clutters and introduce a new female character, sixteen-year-old Nancy. One of the scenes finishes: «A car horn honked. At last – Dick», – another scene begins: «Good grief, Kenyon! I hear you!» (*Capote, 1994, p. 17*). The critic D. Guest states that Capote's notes employ the language of cinematography, moving from one paragraph of description to another with the phrase «Cut to» (*Hickman, 2005, p.467*). The background – death row and stories of other prisoners – is «the Griffith cross-cutting», a cinematographic technique Capote employed (*Nance, 1973, p. 188*).

The leading structural technique employed by Capote through most of the novel is a kind of cinematic contrast. One of the scenes in Part One finishes with the hysterical testimony of the habitant of Holcomb: «They were dead. A whole family. Gentle, kindly people, people I knew – murdered» (*Capote, 1994, p. 66*). Another scene begins with the irrelevant observations: «Eight non-stop passenger trains hurry through Holcomb every twenty-four hours» (*Capote, 1994, p. 66*). Then the scene goes to the mail messenger, Mrs. Sadie Truitt, whose Sunday morning is a workday like any other, she was astonished to see two ambulances cross the railroad tracks and turn toward the Clutter property. Capote concludes Part One with Perry and Dick four hundred miles away, sleeping.

The next scene looks as a cinematic contrast, too: Dewey pauses at an upstairs window, he notices, out in a wheat field, a scarecrow on which an old dress of Bonnie's flutters in the wind. It reminds him of a dream his wife described to him a few mornings before. Once she told him she was in her kitchen when Bonnie walked through the door. Suddenly Capote changes the shot, he tells us about Perry and Dick walking along the highway and singing because of the feeling of despair.

Properly speaking, the author reinforces the contrast between victims and killers by (vignette structure), cinematic or not. In other words, he reinforces by repeated jolts from one group to the other. The section preceding the murders is an example of this technique. Minutes before Perry and Dick reach the Clutter house, they are shown at a gas station where Perry has been nursing his grotesquely injured legs in the men's room. «Perry gripped the edge of the wash basin and hauled himself to a standing position. His legs trembled; the pain in his knees made him perspire. He wiped his face with a paper towel. He unlocked the door and said, "O.K. Let's go"» (*Capote, 1994, p. 272*). The next scene begins with the description Nancy's bedroom. «Nancy's bedroom was the smallest, most personal room in the house—girlish, and as frothy as a ballerina's tutu. Walls, ceiling, and everything else except a bureau and a writing desk, were pink or blue or white» (*Capote, 1994, p. 272*). This juxtaposition vividly anticipates the rapidly approaching moment (not to be described in detail until much later in the book) when these men will enter Nancy's bedroom with intentions of rape and murder (of one of them, Dick). The author chooses definite episodes, details and shows them vividly and in details. Such short sections contrast with four main parts of the novel.

The portrayal of Smith among the people in the courtroom is also contrast. «Only Perry Smith, who owned neither jacket nor tie, seemed sartorially misplaced» (*Capote, 1994, p. 272*). The other contrast is the Clutters' belief in God opposed to ethical and philosophical vacuous souls of the murderers. Everybody can see these contrasts as a juxtaposition of light and dark, optimistic and pessimistic, art and ruin. The image of a positive, successful and respectable Clutter family is opposed to the images of negative, unsuccessful and aggressive Perry Smith and Dick Hickock. The last one understands this opposition and in Part Three the reader finds the evidence: «Envy was constantly with him» (*Capote, 1994, p. 200*). Contrast scenes prove the author's deliberate use of cinematic experience and show the connections between the main events in the novel.

In Part Two Capote introduces detective Alvin Dewey and this part covers the first month of investigation. The obvious reason of all the difficulties of the crime is the absence of a motive for the crime. The author describes the ceremony of the Clutters' funeral. Due to parallel cutting we keep an eye on Perry and Dick. At the same time the author tells the reader about an early period of Perry's life and his emotional growth, in particular his crippled infancy and youth. The technique of parallel cutting is employed as a cinematic one by the writer deliberately.

Capote titled Part Three simply «Answer». The part begins with the introduction Of Floyd Wells, the informer, and his statement to authorities implicating Dick and Perry. This makes this part culminating: at last we know why the young men have arrived in Holcomb. Since this point the tension in the novel becomes weaker. Capote heightens the effect of immediacy by narrating the confession scene in the present tense. The author transfers the readers to his characters' thoughts. As a rule, he employs contrast descriptions masterly to make a situation or a character diverse (but he keeps to the realistic credibility) – he always emphasizes everything he portrays isn't ordinary

and can't be accounted. The entire confession scene has been narrated from Dewey's point of view.

Part Three ends with a short section describing the arrival of the prisoners in Garden City. The drama finishes along with the departure of the mild autumn that furnished the backdrop for the principal events of the novel.

Part Four is entitled «The Corner», after the prisoners' name for the execution chamber at the Kansas State Penitentiary. The last part is a complete epic structure. The Clutters and their murderers are dead; Judge Tate, who announced death penalty to Smith and Hickock, died of pneumonia. Bobby Rupp got married. Inspector Elvin Dewey encountered Susan Kidwell at the cemetery whom he had last seen as a child at the time of the trial. The scene concludes with the detective's emotional thought, Nancy might have been an alive, nice, pretty and young woman. Dewey watched «...as she disappeared down the path, a pretty girl in a hurry, her smooth hair swinging, shining – just such a young woman as Nancy might have been. Then, starting home, he walked toward the trees, and under them, leaving behind him the big sky, the whisper of wind voices in the wind-bent wheat» (*Capote, 1994, p. 352*). The mood of the narration changes, too.

The novel evolved from the life itself. It is its natural continuation and it ends just formally, in reality it returns to this life. That's why the writer must have regulated the introduction and the ending of the book. Capote employs double-ended shot narrative that intensifies the principal theme of the novel. The bounds of the novel are broader than the narration about the fate of Perry Smith: as the author wants the narration continues and the described story turns out to be a part of a general picture of life that is the centre of the author's attention.

The motion from the exposition to the denouement is still a moment of the unstoppable life getting over the difficulties of a fate. The final returns us to the description of wheat fields, the Clutter family, Susan Kidwell, Bobby Rupp. It is a compositional repetition (the novel begins and ends with the close-ups) makes the narration harmonious and complete, enlarges the depicted events and helps to achieve high artistic merit.

Due to the parallel and contrast cutting of different scenes, a number of close-ups, retrospection, shots on the run and the details of background T. Capote «enlivens» the script he moves and organizes the story. Different things fall under his eye paying attention to their brightness and spatial location. The example of this, the description of the Clutters' house, is an emblematic personification of the owners' life. The atmosphere of intense nostalgia, of silent, haunted rooms, is one Capote handles well. He makes the scene vivid with sensory images and precise, intimate details recalling the departed tenants. Due to stereoscopic spatial reality and a definite sound row, the result is a verbal equivalent of cinematic *mise en scene*: «Inside, the house was warm, for the heat had not been turned off, and the shiny-floored rooms, smelling of a lemon-scented polish, seemed only temporarily untenanted; it was as though today were Sunday and the family might at any moment return from church. <...> In the parlor, a sheet of music, "Comin' Thro' the Rye," stood open on the piano rack. In the hall, a sweat-stained gray Stetson hat – Herb's – hung on a hat peg. Upstairs in Kenyon's room, on a shelf above his bed, the lenses of the dead boy's spectacles gleamed with reflected light» (*Capote, 1994, p. 152*).

Slow descriptions-shots in Capote's novel follow the same aims as in the cinema: so that a reader may feel the «depicted time» in the shot better, understand hidden content and examine the mise en scene attentively. The distinguishing characteristic of the slow text is slow rhythm. By means of which the author creates slow passing of time and slow portrayals. Rhythmic constructions are widely used in the novel. The text lets the reader feel the depicted reality. The writer reconstructs the reality and transforms it into the fiction documentary world of the book masterly. Visual imagination is an important and indispensable component of the process of writing for Capote. The vividness of his characters, their expressiveness, uniqueness and emotional saturation depend on the writer's skills to visualize everything. Capote encodes his visions into the words masterly so that the reader may perceive the text reproducing the visions more adequately.

The work is full of various visualizations and auditory images. It improves a high level of cinematic thinking of Capote. His characters appeal to the reader's thinking and his image memory. As to the technique of portraying the writer focuses upon the insignificant but vivid external detail and «unfocuses» the portrait characteristic throughout the novel. This technique helps us see everything as a whole and understand the human nature in different ways. The following description has anxious character: «...the left eye being truly serpentine, with venomous, sickly-blue squint» (*Capote, 1994, p. 31*).

Striving for achieving the cinematic effect the author employs the sounds. The nonfiction has an audiovisual character. For example, the reader sees a haunted execution chamber, gallows and an executioner from Dewey's point of view. The conversations of the people invited to the ceremony seemed to be the «self-consciously casual conversation». The scene is accompanied by the sound detail – rain rapping the high warehouse roof. The sound, not unlike the rat-a-tat-tat of parade drums, heralded Hickock's arrival. The impression of solemn ritual prepares the reader for the climactic scene. Thus, the scenes of the novel are filled with sounds and promote reader's imagination and empathy.

The most important and finest means of realization of the hidden meanings of the text is its sound orchestration. Capote thought of his writing in musical terms; the above stated rather short but expressive scene in the house of the Clutter family. The author was fond of «glissando endings» that avoid the climactic organ note. He cited the end of «In Cold Blood» as an example, but the end of Part Three would serve as well. The passage begins with one of his more gratuitous, though strictly factual, touches – a description of two Garden City tomcats «...using their paws as though they are surgical instruments, the cats extract from the grilles every feathery particle <...> who are always together» and whose daily ceremony is to scavenge the grilles of parked cars in search of «slaughtered birds» picked up on the highway (*Capote, 1994, p. 246*). Their unvarying daily itinerary takes them to Courthouse Square, «another of their hunting grounds – a highly promising one on the afternoon of Wednesday, January 6, for the area swarmed with Finney County vehicles that had brought to town part of the crowd populating the square» (*Capote, 1994, p. 255*). It is such a picturesque and exotic scene.

The final part of the book – an original musical coda – summarizes the previous coherence of the author's idea. Almost all the objects are repeated in comparison with the beginning of the novel: the Clutter family, Kidwell, Rupp, Dewey, wheat fields. Moreover, the objects at the beginning of the novel are just descriptions or a

storytelling, then they become a dramatic conclusion due to the intensity of the inner lyricism: in the final there is the author's thought about the end of life. The final shows the artist's sense of beauty and grandeur of life. The serious meaning of the final images intensifies drama and fatality, but their art expressiveness, musical smoothness contrast it. Every living thing strives for new life.

The intonation of Capote's narration is diverse. It is both bare listing of facts and lyric reminiscences and journalistic chronicle. They all make up uniqueness of the artist. The scene of waiting for the criminals is an example: «High-school students, among them former classmates of Nancy and Kenyon Clutter, chanted cheerleader rhymes, bubbled bubble gum, gobbled hotdogs and soda pop. Mothers soothed wailing babies. Men strolled about with young children perched on their shoulders. The Boy Scouts were present – an entire troop. And the middle-aged membership of a women's bridge club arrived en masse» (*Capote, 1994, p. 247*). Laconic language of reportage reproduces real events as if it edits separate clips of the reality. The author causes the illusion of the reader's participation in these events. So, the organic unity of the text is achieved due to the rhythm showing the passing of the time in the shot and the tension of the course of events.

The author focuses on details which are not random. Every description and biography are necessary, all the moments that slow the event are significant.

«Cinematic» thinking of the writer helps him portray psychological state of the characters. For example, Smith's face: «Each angle of it induced a different impression. It was a change-face, and mirror-guided experiments had taught him how to ring the changes, how to look now ominous, now impish, now soulful; a tilt of the head, a twist of the lips, and the corrupt gypsy became the gentle romantic» (*Capote, 1994, p. 15–16*). Sometimes unconscious motions of the soul, mood, gradual accumulation of disappointment and offence, that is our inner life we can't describe and analyze – feelings of grief, hidden agitation, dissatisfaction, sometimes fear, misgivings and sometimes, vice versa, excitement and striving for better – left its mark on his face. Capote creates a realistic visual image masterly. Every «shot» where he portrayed Perry has psychologism and drama in every situation. Due to these techniques the author managed to show the character's serious spirit. Every scene just completes it. All the scenes cause the reader's sympathy.

By means of visual inserted descriptions – letters, dreams, documents, notes, landscapes and so on – we can see a psychological content and implication of the other scenes. It is the secret of their informational content. The writer portrays the landscape, shows the colours, smells, surrounding environment laconically. He creates complete visual and audio images. For example, Christmas comes, unseasonably mild and brilliant, days seem to be unlikely beautiful – dry air, bright sun, blue sky but Clutter's house «was deprived of the late owner's dedicated attention, the first threads of decay's cobweb were being spun. A gravel rake lay rusting in the driveway; the lawn was parched and shabby» (*Capote, 1994, p. 206*). The shot helps create visual image and it slows down the events.

The narrator's vision belongs to the cinematic techniques the author uses. The factual aspect of the narrative, remaining unseen made it possible to use a panoptic / supervisory / cinematic gaze. The reader interprets the events and characters through it. It makes the effect of filming by one camera. The reader sees just a cinematic gaze throughout the whole text. The supervisory narrator changes the manner of telling

dependent on the circumstances and locale easily but he stays the creator and an interested narrator of the fiction reality invariably. The art functions of the narrator are obvious in the narrative bounds of the sections of the novel. He orchestrates and comments upon the events, shifts the reader and himself from one place to another, from one character to the other; and he finds the true sense of the case in the chaos of events, documents and gossip. Tom Wolfe stated «Capote was employing the technique of presenting every scene to the reader through the eyes of a particular character, giving the reader the feeling of being inside the character's mind and experiencing the emotional reality of the scene....» (*see Mass, 2000*).

The panoptic gaze as more specifically cinematic controls Capote's text. The panoptic gaze follows Perry and Dick, that's why they are readily available to the reader's gaze. The author supervises the killers even to the point of probing their damaged psyches. The writer employs the panoptic gaze to conclude that some mental dysfunction dealt Smith and Hickock. Capote must also exert his supervisory and panoptic forces on the Clutter family. Only by controlling and managing the Clutters' sphere of power as well as Smith and Hickock will be pushed to their full criminal potential.

Capote draws his panoptic net tightly around the Clutter family, almost as if they might otherwise escape their murderous destiny and foil the spectacle Capote plans for his readers. Part One titled «The Last to See Them Alive» highlights the significance of his supervision of what will happen to the Clutters: not only will they be «seen» in sharpest, most intrusive detail, but these views will be the «last», as a carefully predetermined number of minutes ticks down to their excruciating and inevitable demise. This title casts the Clutters as death row prisoners in their final hours before execution, where everything is final – the final day at work, the final meal, the final date, and so on – and the Clutters are the only ones who don't know it.

The panoptic narrator makes an impression as if the writer narrated everything what the reader thought of, as if the reader created the narration himself. Since the author remained unseen, he doesn't conclude. Capote's detachment seems to be explained by two reasons: the reader should draw conclusions from the philosophical social and psychological circumstances of the multiple murder by himself but the author doesn't want to prevent the reader from drawing conclusions from the murderers.

Cinema is present in the novel as an intertext: the allusions of the movies appear in Smith's mind, especially the movie «Treasure of Sierra Madre». The author's notes reveal that he shared this cinematographic orientation with Perry Smith, who also wanted to think of Capote's emergent narrative in terms of a film, even asking Capote at one point «was there anyone from the cinema world there» to see him (*see Hickman, 2005, p. 475*).

Conclusion. Nonfiction novel «In Cold Blood» provokes genre associations with cinematography (road movies) due to the cinematic techniques. Employing the cinematic techniques drew a wide response of the critics. According to our research this feature of Capote's work isn't an obvious attempt to follow the fashion but in the first place it is one of the models of the author's visions. The specific character of visual and local color of Capote's artistic thinking: his palette of the characters is mainly visual, we can see pictorial – painting and cinematic – visions of the materials realized by fiction techniques. The author describes the plot of the novel as a video filming, he orchestrates the events shifting different scenes using the techniques of slowing down and

repetitions, a variety of pans, zooms and cut, flashbacks and so on. Cutting is the principle technique to create the content coherence, a tool of selection and combination of the details which are the most significant due to their information value. The research doesn't cover all the complexity of the given problem. Nonfiction novel gives perspective to study further the artistic potential of the use of the cinematic techniques and means in the documentary narrative.

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